

Gender Differences in Resilience, Compassionate for Others and Humanity, Positive and Negative Affect Among Higher Secondary Students

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Abstract:-

➤ **Introduction**

Boy and Girl students in secondary schools differ greatly in terms of flexibility, adaptability to situations, compassion for others, positive and negative influences in thinking, etc. Both negative and positive influence can be seen in the classroom of students i.e. they girls students think negatively when they fail in the exam or when the marks are low but for the boys students they see the marks very incidentally i.e. think they can take care of it in the next street. If the teachers do not provide enough time during the assignment, the girls will feel a lot of tension, but the boy students have the ability to install, so they are the students' ability. Therefore, the environment should be created in the classroom to develop the character of the students. If they fail in the exam, this study was done with the aim of creating an environment to develop the resilience, develop positive thinking and develop the compassionate towards others. A study was conducted to know his power of compassionate to negative and positive thoughts and for resilience for students.

➤ **Need for the study:**

In today's scenario, it can be seen that only if students are given flexibility, they will participate in the classroom with enthusiasm. Students also develop negative thoughts if they stay at home. Due to negative thoughts, compassion towards others is lost in the student. After growing up, this trait has a great impact on the society. So growing up in a flexible environment measures the positive or negative thoughts of the students and grows up with positive thinking this topic is chosen by the researcher to measure how the child reacts to others or feels lost when compassionate others when suffering. The study has been conducted to find out whether the student has the resilience to endure adversity and develop the positive thinking to bounce back to students.

➤ **Sample :**

Samples were randomly collected from three different schools, i.e. Government Schools, Government Aided Schools and Private Schools in the Chennai District from XI std and XII std in Arts and Science group. Total no of sample 757.

➤ **Tools:**

Research tools taken the study Resilience, compassionate for others humanity and Positive affect and Negative affect.

I. INTRODUCTION

People who are more satisfied by their lives tend to experience greater physical and psychological health than people who are less satisfied with their lives. From an economic point of view, it is important to know what causes people to be satisfied with their lives. From a psychological perspective, understanding mental health is an important theoretical and empirical undertaking. Man in the world today faces difficulty to maintain a good balanced mental health because of rapid neutralization and sophistication of the modern social system. Thus an individual often fails to maintain a balance between himself and his social environment and also understands a link between mental health and emotion.

Boy and Girl students in secondary schools differ greatly in terms of flexibility, adaptability to situations, compassion for others, positive and negative influences in thinking, etc. Both negative and positive influence can be seen in the classroom of students i.e. they girls students think negatively when they fail in the exam or when the marks are low but for the boys students they see the marks very incidentally i.e. think they can take care of it in the next street. If the teachers do not provide enough time during the assignment, the girls will feel a lot of tension, but the boy students have the ability to install, so they are the students' ability. Therefore, the environment should be created in the classroom to develop the character of the students. If they fail in the exam, this study was done with the aim of creating an environment to develop the resilience, develop positive thinking and develop the compassionate towards others. A study was conducted to know his power of compassionate to negative and positive thoughts and for resilience for students

A. **Sample:**

Samples were randomly collected from three different schools, i.e. Government Schools, Government Aided Schools and Private Schools in the Chennai District from XI std and XII std in Arts and Science group. From Arts group 442 students (Boys 241 and girls 201) and Science group 334 students (Boys 164 and girls 170). In the case of government school there are 40 boys and 48 girls in arts and 31 boys and 24 girls in science groups from XI standard and 43 boys and 24 girls in arts and 35 boys and 30 girls in science groups

from XII standard are selected. In the case of government aided school there are 48 boys and 44 girls in arts and 23 boys and 20 girls in science groups from XI standard and 45 boys and 37 girls in arts and 20 boys and 23 girls in science groups from XII standard are selected and In the case of private school there are 25 boys and 25 girls in arts and 27 boys and 26 girls in science groups from XI standard and 40 boys and 23 girls in arts and 28 boys and 47 girls in science groups from XII standard are selected. Convenient random selection is done in all the cases from the total population of 1582 students.

B. Pilot study:

In order to standardize the tools taken for the study all the tool were given to 50 students at the beginning of the study, then reliability and validity of the tools were calculated based on the scores obtained through pilot study.

C. Resilience :

We all face adversity and other stressors but it's how we deal with it that matters to develop resilience during difficult times.

We need to develop the ability to accept and cope with whatever we receive. To develop the character of accepting and coping with difficult situations as well as how to accept happy situations with joy. Students should be prepared to be Resilience in life.

1) Increase interaction time with parents and peers to see how parents approach a problem as well as how peers handle their problem.

2) When the score falls or fails in the exam, one should see why the score fell and diligently follow the steps to increase the score in the next exam and avoid negative thoughts.

3) Avoiding situations that disturb us i.e. avoiding friends who interfere with our studies Negative thinking that causes fear overtime to avoid failure.

4) Avoid stressful situations during exams with exam attitude.

D. Compassionate love for close others and Humanity:

Students should develop from childhood the ability to help others when they are in distress and develop awareness of the suffering of others. Problems faced during student life are common to all so we should see if there are any ways to reduce the problem and also when others are suffering like us. When approaching other people's problems, you need to see them from their point of view. We should avoid making fun of our friends when they fail Give some strategies to get good marks give some advice to relieve our friend's suffering. One must realize that life is not an environment to live peacefully while growing up with negative thoughts. By being kind to others, they will be kind to us and thus we can change our situation into a happy one. When dealing with an issue one should be emotional and be situational. We all are running towards our goals but we should be careful not to disturb others.

E. Positive Affect and Negative Affect:

The impact of positive and negative thoughts on students in secondary schools is discussed in all periods. Happiness is a positive affect in an emotional state. That is, getting a good score in the exam has a positive effect of happiness, At the same time anger or fear occurs when failing an exam which is a negative affect. This effect has gender difference and abundance and less fear of exam failure among Girl students and less among Boy students. When looking at the gender difference, the positive impact is seen more by the students. Most of us believe that positive feelings are the opposite of negative feelings, and that a person who is unhappy is also sad. These statements are truisms in the language of feelings, affects, and emotions, as fundamental in one plus one equals two.

Positive and negative affect are present in all stages of our daily life Positive emotions increase our performance while negative affect also makes us watch our brain functions. We can see a situation where Girl students are more afraid of studying than Boy students in terms of fear of test scores.

F. Definition of Variables

➤ Resilience is the process of successfully adapting to a difficult or challenging situation with mental fortitude. A resilient student will have trait interests such as self-awareness, realistic thinking, stress avoidance strategies, self-control, and confident problem solving.

➤ Compassionate Fo Other Humanity

Compassion is a feeling that motivates us to understand the feelings of the suffering person and do what we can to alleviate their suffering. Refers to a more general ability to understand and feel emotions in others.

➤ Positive Affect And Negative Affect:

Positive affect gives a positive emotion such as happiness, excitement, pride, the idea of being able to remember, and the achievement of a desired object. Physical fatigue is not felt in an exciting situation and we can feel physical discomfort in an unwilling place.

Negative effects include anxiety, sadness, fear, anger, and shame. For example, when the teacher asks in front of others that you don't know how to read, it creates a negative effect of shame on the students. Being nervous on the exam day is a negative influence.

G. Need for the study :

In today's scenario, it can be seen that only if students are given flexibility, they will participate in the classroom with enthusiasm. Students also develop negative thoughts if they stay at home. Due to negative thoughts, compassion towards others is lost in the student. After growing up, this trait has a great impact on the society. So growing up in a flexible environment measures the positive or negative thoughts of the students and grows up with positive thinking this topic is chosen by the researcher to measure how the child reacts to others or feels lost when compassionate others when

suffering. The study has been conducted to find out whether the student has the resilience to endure adversity and develop the positive thinking to bounce back to students.

H. Statement of the Problem

The topic for the present research is entitled as ‘gender differences in resilience, compassionate, positive and negative affect among higher secondary students’

I. Objectives

- To find out impact of Resilience, Compassionate Positive Affect and Negative Affect, among Higher Secondary School students.

J. Hypothesis

- There are no significant difference between boys and Girls in Resilience, Compassionate positive affect and Negative affect

K. Statistical Analysis

Critical ratio is used to analyze the data

➤ **Hypothesis**

- There are no significant differences between boys and Girls in Resilience, Compassionate for others, positive affect and Negative affect among higher secondary students

Table 1:- Table showing the multiple comparison of resilience within various sub groups classified on the basis of Gender

36.15School	Class	Group	Gender	No.	Mean	S.D	'C.R'
Govt.	XI	Arts	Boys	40	126.98	24.76	0.723
			Girls	48	125.83	18.73	
		Science	Boys	31	121.13	19.37	1.318
			Girls	24	130.6	14.3	
	XII	Arts	Boys	43	128.0	17.66	0.419
			Girls	24	136.13	18.31	
		Science	Boys	35	122.7	20.79	0.64
			Girls	30	134.48	26.91	
Govt. Aided	XI	Arts	Boys	48	126.08	15.71	4.059
			Girls	44	117.15	9.29	
		Science	Boys	23	115.37	11.68	2.67
			Girls	20	112.31	13.3	
	XII	Arts	Boys	45	115.72	12.78	2.96
			Girls	37	114.34	35.92	
		Science	Boys	20	119.25	14.74	0.607
			Girls	23	118.57	15.57	
Private	XI	Arts	Boys	25	131.96	30.25	1.066
			Girls	25	132.89	22.93	
		Science	Boys	27	125.04	19.62	0.289
			Girls	26	157.2	18.53	
	XII	Arts	Boys	40	119.7	26.5	0.652
			Girls	23	97.6	32.56	
		Science	Boys	28	130.8	17.17	2.151
			Girls	47	129.3	21.7	

From table 1, it is clear that the calculated 't' values are lower than that of table 't' values in the case of Boys and Girls of Arts and Science group from XI and XII std., in Government School. Hence the Hypothesis is accepted in the case of Boys and Girls of Arts and Science group from XI and XII std., in Government School. It is proved that there is no significant difference with Resilience scores.

Prior studies indicate that gender has a notable effect on a children's coping strategies (2, 3). Coping strategies can be categorized into two basic types; maladaptive and adaptive strategies (P. Hampel & Petermann, 2005). Younger boys and girls, and boys from all age groups tend to make more use of adaptive coping strategies that focus on the immediate problem. Strategies are externalised and commonly include direct action, distraction and positive self-instruction (P. Hampel & Petermann, 2005; P. Hampel & Petermann, 2006).

From table, it is clear that the calculated 't' values are greater than that of table 't' values in the case of Boys and

Girls of Arts and Science group from XI standard and Boys and Girls of Arts group from XII standard in Government Aided School. Hence the hypothesis is rejected and proved that there is significant difference between boys and girls on their Cognitive Style scores in Arts and Science group from XI standard and Arts group from XII standard from Government Aided School.

The Hypothesis is accepted in the case of Boys and Girls of Science group from XII Std. in Government Aided School. It is proved that there is no significant difference with Resilience scores in these cases.

From table, it is clear that the calculated 't' values are greater than that of table 't' values in the case of Boys and Girls of Science group from XII std., in Private School. Hence the hypothesis is rejected and proved that there is significant difference between boys and girls on their

Resilience scores in Science group from XII standard in Private School.

The Hypothesis is accepted in the case of Boys and Girls of Arts and Science group from XI Std. and Arts group from XII Std. in Private School. It is proved that there is no significant difference with Resilience scores in these cases.

Prior studies indicate that gender has a notable effect on a childrens coping strategies (2, 3). Coping strategies can be categorised into two basic types; maladaptive and adaptive strategies (P. Hampel & Petermann, 2005). Younger boys and girls, and boys from all age groups tend to make more use of adaptive coping strategies that focus on the immediate problem. Strategies are externalised and commonly include

direct action, distraction and positive self-instruction (P. Hampel & Petermann, 2005; P. Hampel & Petermann, 2006).

There is also evidence that girls cope with daily stressors by seeking social support and utilising social resources (Frydenberg & Lewis, 1993). In contrast, boys use physical recreation such as sport to cope with adversity (Frydenberg & Lewis, 1993).

Despite being under stress, girls have been found to use resilience factors such as seeking and getting support more than boys, with Grotberg finding that girls used these resilience factors more than boys (P. Hampel & Petermann, 2005).

Table 2 showing the multiple comparison of compassionate love for close others and humanity within various sub group classified on the basis of Gender

School	Class	Group	Gender	No.	Mean	S.D	'p'
Govt.	XI	Arts	Boys	40	114.04	18.46	0.92
			Girls	48	117.8	19.75	
		Science	Boys	31	110.93	21.5	0.599
			Girls	24	113.79	13.75	
	XII	Arts	Boys	43	116.25	21.34	2.18
			Girls	24	124.92	11.14	
		Science	Boys	35	114.54	18.22	1.70
			Girls	30	123.13	21.86	
Govt. Aided	XI	Arts	Boys	48	114.56	12.23	1.126
			Girls	44	111.46	14.01	
		Science	Boys	23	115.03	15.99	0.076
			Girls	20	115.35	11.56	
	XII	Arts	Boys	45	115.72	21.42	1.244
			Girls	37	109.35	24.34	
		Science	Boys	20	108.75	17.13	0.804
			Girls	23	113.04	17.78	
Private	XI	Arts	Boys	25	120.71	22.91	0.526
			Girls	25	123.66	16.14	
		Science	Boys	27	116.61	17.07	0.586
			Girls	26	113.84	17.36	
	XII	Arts	Boys	40	104.13	24.56	0.566
			Girls	23	107.38	20.28	
		Science	Boys	28	124.9	13.19	2.709
			Girls	47	112.43	26.52	

From table, it is clear that the calculated 't' values are greater than that of table 't' values in the case of Boys and Girls of Arts group from XII std., in Government School. Hence the hypothesis is rejected and proved that there is significant difference between boys and girls on their Compassion scores in Arts group from XII standard in Private School.

The Hypothesis is accepted in the case of Boys and Girls of Arts and Science group from XI Std. and Science group from XII Std. in Government School. It is proved that there is no significant difference with Compassion scores in these cases.

From table, it is clear that the calculated 't' values are lower than that of table 't' values in the case of Boys and Girls

of Arts and Science group from XI and XII std., in Government Aided School. Hence the Hypothesis is accepted in the case of Boys and Girls of Arts and Science group from XI and XII std., in Government Aided School. It is proved that there is no significant difference with Compassion scores.

From table, it is clear that the calculated 't' values are greater than that of table 't' values in the case of Boys and Girls of Science group from XII std., in Private School. Hence the hypothesis is rejected and proved that there is significant difference between boys and girls on their Compassion scores in Science group from XII standard in Private School.

The Hypothesis is accepted in the case of Boys and Girls of Arts and Science group from XI Std. and Arts group from

XII Std. in Private School. It is proved that there is no significant difference with Compassion scores in these cases.

Table 3 showing the multiple comparison of positive affect within various sub group classified on the basis of Gender

School	Class	Group	Gender	No.	Mean	S.D	'p'
Govt.	XI	Arts	Boys	40	39.24	5.76	0.427
			Girls	48	38.69	6.29	
		Science	Boys	31	38.64	6.79	0.97
			Girls	24	38.36	6.29	
	XII	Arts	Boys	43	38.72	6.8	0.2688
			Girls	24	38.33	4.97	
		Science	Boys	35	37.23	5.52	3.61
			Girls	30	41.38	3.66	
Govt. Aided	XI	Arts	Boys	48	41.44	5.5	4.428
			Girls	44	35.65	6.89	
		Science	Boys	23	41.07	5.61	1.33
			Girls	20	39.06	4.26	
	XII	Arts	Boys	45	36.14	5.46	2.48
			Girls	37	39.0	4.93	
		Science	Boys	20	37.75	6.94	0.38
			Girls	23	37.0	5.75	
Private	XI	Arts	Boys	25	39.65	5.41	0.438
			Girls	25	40.36	6.03	
		Science	Boys	27	39.91	5.19	1.87
			Girls	26	37.3	4.96	
	XII	Arts	Boys	40	37.09	6.17	0.9
			Girls	23	38.57	6.33	
		Science	Boys	28	37.86	4.65	0.405
			Girls	47	38.39	5.94	

Table 4 showing the multiple comparison of negative affect within various sub group classified on the basis of Gender

School	Class	Group	Gender	No.	Mean	S.D	'p'
Govt.	XI	Arts	Boys	40	35.3	4.78	0.872
			Girls	48	34.31	5.86	
		Science	Boys	31	36.87	6.62	1.58
			Girls	24	39.86	7.2	
	XII	Arts	Boys	43	21.19	8.03	9.08
			Girls	24	37.04	6.09	
		Science	Boys	35	37.37	6.91	1.73
			Girls	30	34.32	7.19	
Govt. Aided	XI	Arts	Boys	48	39.96	4.74	3.35
			Girls	44	35.89	6.65	
		Science	Boys	23	41.92	4.0	2.56
			Girls	20	44.81	3.39	
	XII	Arts	Boys	45	41.27	4.88	7.39
			Girls	37	33.22	4.93	
		Science	Boys	20	36.03	6.2	0.55
			Girls	23	37.14	7.04	
Private	XI	Arts	Boys	25	36.15	6.23	0.17
			Girls	25	36.47	6.89	
		Science	Boys	27	36.96	5.27	0.39
			Girls	26	37.55	5.48	
	XII	Arts	Boys	40	36.58	6.34	0.405
			Girls	23	36.0	4.91	
		Science	Boys	28	39.39	5.06	0.683
			Girls	47	38.48	6.36	

The Hypothesis is accepted in the case of Boys and Girls of Arts and Science group from XI Std, and Boys and Girls of Arts and group from XII Std. in Government School. It is proved that there is no significant difference with Positive Affect scores in these cases.

Affect intensity (AI) may reconcile 2 seemingly paradoxical findings: Women report more negative affect than men but equal happiness as men. AI describes people's varying response intensity to identical emotional stimuli. A college sample of 66 women and 34 men was assessed on both positive and negative affect using 4 measurement methods: self-report, peer report, daily report, and memory performance. A principal-components analysis revealed an affect balance component and an AI component. Multimeasure affect balance and AI scores were created, and t tests were computed that showed women to be as happy as and more intense than men. Gender accounted for less than 1% of the variance in happiness but over 13% in AI. Thus, depression findings of more negative affect in women do not conflict with well-being findings of equal happiness across gender. Generally, women's more intense positive emotions balance their higher negative affect.

II. DISCUSSION

- This study indicates that private school girls' have more test anxiety than boys. But both government and government aided school students have not differ in their test anxiety.
- Students who are studying in all the three type of management ie , government, aided and private school don't show any significant difference in their resilience
- As well as both boys and girls do not show any significant difference in cognitive style, compassionate love for close other and humanity, emotional intelligence, mental health and panas.

III. CONCLUSION

This study shows the determination of mental health and cognitive style of students indicated there is no significant relationship among the variables. Students should be enhanced by resilience , problem solving skill, mental health, emotional intelligence, and panas to develop all over improvement among students. If the educational institutions could be granted the requisite autonomy, they would perhaps become repositories of the nation's culture and lead the nation of greater hights.

REFERENCES

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